

ISic1101

I.Sicily inscription 1101

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

base

Editor

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Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2002.07.01

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Eryx

Place of origin (modern)

Erice

Provenance

Said to have been recovered from a well or cistern in the vicinity of the Chiesa di San Pietro

Coordinates

38.0375951,12.5878279

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Erice, Biblioteca Civica "Vito Carvini", inventory 213

Physical Description

An off-white quadrangular block, broken in half in the past and rejoined together. The right-hand half is more worn than the left, with the line of the break running vertically through the middle of the text. The stone appears to be more or less intact on the upper half, but broken / damaged to an unquantifiable degree around the lower edges. The sides have been pecked with a chisel implying the presence originally of blocks or other material to each side. The upper surface appears smooth.

Dimensions

Height c.30 cm

Width c.90 cm

Depth c.48 cm

Layout

Four lines of Greek filling the full width of the stone, with a vacat below

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. ἐπὶ ταμία Λευκίου Καικιλίου
2. Λευκίου υἱοῦ Μετέλλου(vac.undefinied)
3. Πασίων Δεκκίου Σεισυρίων
4. Ἐγεσταῖος χιλιαρχήσας

Apparatus

Text from autopsy (Prag)

The stone reads Δευκίου

Translation (en)

In the quaestorship of Lucius Caecilius Metellus, son of Lucius: Pasion Seisurion, son of Dekkios, Segestan, having served as chiliarch

Commentary

The block is presumably part of a dedication to Venus Erycina, made by a member of the Segestan elite who served as a military commander during the period of the Roman Republican province. It is likely that this was to commemorate his service as the Sicilian commander of the honorific garrison of 200 men stationed at Eryx, described by Diodorus Siculus (4.83.7), as well as Cicero (Verr. 5.124), and for which the 17 Sicilian towns that had remained most loyal to Rome were responsible (see Prag, JRS 2007 [<https://www.jstor.org/stable/20430572>] pp. 81-82 with references). A similar text can be seen in CIL 10.7258 = ISic0538 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0538>]. The name Pasion [http://clas-igpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/igpn_search.cgi?namenoaccents=%CE%A0%CE%91%CE%A3%CE%99%CE%A9%CE%9D] is moderately well attested in Sicily as well as in the wider Greek world, whereas Seisurion is assumed to be an indigenous form. The Lucius Caecilius L.f. Metellus in question is normally identified with the son of the Metellus who governed Sicily after Verres, in 70 BC, and who held the quaestorship referred to here in 52 BC, as by Broughton and others (see <http://romanrepublic.ac.uk/person/2480> [<http://romanrepublic.ac.uk/person/2480>]).

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